

ACCURACY AND REGULATORY-LEGAL ISSUES IN TOPOGRAPHIC SURVEYING USING DRONES

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes accuracy and regulatory issues arising in topographic surveying using Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs — drones). The study examines the impact of geodetic referencing, photogrammetric processing, and atmospheric factors in the creation of Digital Elevation Models (DEM) and orthophoto maps based on aerial imagery. In addition, the legal framework governing drone usage and the need for its improvement are discussed. The research results contribute to the development of scientific recommendations for the effective application of UAV technologies in geodetic practice.

Keywords: UAV, drone, photogrammetry, orthophoto, Digital Elevation Model, accuracy, geodetic control point, regulatory framework.

In recent years, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) have been widely used in geodesy and cartography. Drones make it possible to capture large areas in a short time with high accuracy. Modern devices, particularly drones manufactured by DJI, are extensively applied in geodetic and engineering works. However, the use of UAV technologies involves several challenges related to accuracy, data processing, and legal regulation.

Moreover, UAV technologies are increasingly integrated with photogrammetry, LiDAR, and multispectral imaging methods. This integration enables not only the creation of topographic maps and orthophotos but also digital elevation models (DEM/DTM), volume calculations (e.g., in mining), and vegetation index analysis in agriculture.

Advantages of UAV-based Topographic Surveying:

1. Rapid coverage of large territories
2. High spatial resolution imagery (GSD up to a few centimeters)
3. Reduced human factor influence
4. Accessibility to hard-to-reach areas
5. Lower cost compared to traditional aerial surveying

At the same time, this technology has certain technical and organizational limitations.

Factors Affecting UAV Measurement Accuracy:

1. **Insufficient Ground Control Points (GCPs)** To improve the accuracy of UAV imagery, ground control points are essential. If they are insufficient or inaccurately measured, positional accuracy decreases.

2. **Flight Altitude and Camera Parameters** As flight altitude increases, ground pixel size increases and accuracy decreases. Uncalibrated cameras or lens distortions also affect results.

3. **Photogrammetric Processing Errors** During 3D model and orthophoto generation using specialized software (e.g., Structure-from-Motion algorithms), errors may occur in tie point matching and alignment.

4. **Weather and Lighting Conditions** Wind affects UAV stability, while sun angle and atmospheric conditions influence image contrast and clarity.

5. GNSS Signal Quality In the absence of RTK or PPK technology, coordinate accuracy decreases significantly.

In many countries, UAV operations require special permits and registration. Airspace usage, safety requirements, and restrictions on photographing sensitive objects must be legally regulated. In geodesy, for UAV - derived data to be officially recognized as topographic material, clear accuracy standards and technical regulations must be established. Currently, drones equipped with RTK and PPK technologies provide centimeter-level accuracy. Artificial intelligence–based automatic object detection, terrain modeling, and defect identification systems are rapidly developing. In the future, integrating UAV technologies with national geodetic networks and permanent GNSS stations will further enhance the efficiency and productivity of topographic surveying.

CONCLUSION

Topographic surveying using drones represents an innovative direction in the field of geodesy. Although this technology ensures rapid data acquisition and economic efficiency, there are still challenges related to accuracy and legal regulation. These issues can be mitigated through the use of geodetic control points, the implementation of RTK technology, and the development of standardized accuracy requirements. Therefore, the scientific improvement and methodological development of UAV technologies remain one of the important and actual tasks of modern geodesy.

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